

spacing 5.4-8.1% for 20 x 20 cm, and only 0.7-1.6% for 30 x 30 and 40 x 40 cm.

At the 10- x 10-cm spacing the increase in disease incidence was 171.1% from N₅₀ to N₁₀₀ but only 7.6% from

N₁₀₀ to N₂₀₀.

At the 20- x 20-cm spacing the increase in disease incidence was 137.4% from N₅₀ to N₁₀₀ and 29.1% from N₁₀₀ to N₂₀₀. ■

Data on sheath blight incidence in Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Sheath blight incidence (%) at spacing of			
	10 x 10 cm	20 x 20 cm	30 x 30 cm	40 x 40 cm
N ₀ – Full basal	–	–	–	–
N ₀ – 2 splits	–	–	–	–
N ₀ – 3 splits	–	–	–	–
N ₀ – 4 splits	–	–	–	–
N ₅₀ – Full basal	16.2	2.7	–	–
N ₅₀ – 2 splits	21.6	1.8	–	–
N ₅₀ – 3 splits	19.8	2.6	–	–
N ₅₀ – 4 splits	20.7	2.0	–	–
N ₁₀₀ – Full basal	51.3	4.5	0.9	0.8
N ₁₀₀ – 2 splits	59.4	5.4	0.8	1.0
N ₁₀₀ – 3 splits	52.2	6.3	0.8	0.9
N ₁₀₀ – 4 splits	49.5	5.4	0.7	0.8
N ₂₀₀ – Full basal	58.5	8.1	0.9	1.1
N ₂₀₀ – 2 splits	56.7	7.2	0.8	0.7
N ₂₀₀ – 3 splits	60.3	5.4	1.6	0.9
N ₂₀₀ – 4 splits	53.1	7.2	0.9	0.8

Rice blast — races or virulence frequencies?

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A recent article on races of *Pyricularia oryzae* raises several interesting questions about the current state of understanding of the population genetics and dynamics of the pathogen (Wu, H. K. 1979. Rice blast disease in Taiwan — Race and variety resistance. Tech. Bull. ASPAC Food Fert. Tech. Cent. 48.).

The author advocated the use of the international differential set of rice varieties to monitor changes in the racial composition of blast in Taiwan. He concluded that “race distribution was stable” because the predominant races in 1975-78 were similar to those in 1966.

This conclusion is not necessarily valid because the race frequencies studied involved only the characterization of virulence frequencies corresponding to those of the international differentials. Substantial changes in the racial composition in Taiwan could conceivably have been detected if relevant local varieties had been used as differentials.

The author also commented that “a lot of labor would be saved” if the international differentials were used instead of 12-16 local differentials. Although the labor saving is undeniable, much important information might be lost. It seems more logical to concentrate in the future on the frequencies of relevant pathogen genes rather than on frequencies of largely irrelevant genotypes.

The paper further contended that the disease severity on a rice variety was determined by the “number of its existing virulent races.” A more accurate statement may be that disease severity is determined by the frequency of the corresponding virulence in the pathogen population. This virulence may be present in one or many races. That there is often a direct correlation between the number of virulent races (as determined by an arbitrary set of differentials) that can attack a variety and its susceptibility is merely a statistical artifact of the race concept.

If a variety is susceptible, it may be assumed that the corresponding virulence is high in frequency. There is then a correspondingly high probability

of it being combined with other virulences in the pathogen population. ■

Rice ragged stunt disease in Annamalainagar, Tamil Nadu, India

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References to large-scale occurrence of viral and mycoplasmal diseases on rice have lately been frequent. During routine field visits at the Agricultural Experimental Farm of Annamalai University, the authors detected diseased and stunted plants (culture ARC5752 from IRRRI). The leaves were ragged and serrated, and vein-swelling was marked on the outer surface of the leaf sheath. Flag leaves were small, twisted, and malformed and showed incomplete emergence. Panicle emergence was incomplete and panicles bore mostly chaffy grains. Most of the tillers were branched and produced many panicles. Flowering was delayed and the diseased plant was totally unproductive.

With those characteristic symptoms the disease was suspected to be ragged stunt as described by K.C. Ling [IRRN 2(5) (1977): 6-7]. The disease is reported for the first time from this part of India; however, its occurrence in Coimbatore has been mentioned in a publication of Tamil Nadu Agricultural University. The disease is transmitted and spread by the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal. As the BPH population is increasing in the Cauvery delta, large-scale recurrence of the disease is possible. Hence, suitable prophylactic control measures will be taken up to reduce the BPH populations. ■

Studies on udbatta disease in Karnataka, India

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Udbatta disease caused by *Ephelis oryzae* has occurred in Karnataka State for more than three decades and caused